

MOLECULAR DYNAMICS INVESTIGATION OF RADIATION DAMAGE IN SEMICONDUCTORS

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ABSTRACT

We report the results of a molecular dynamics investigation of the effects of radiation damage on the crystallographic structure of semiconductors. In particular, we consider the formation of point defects and small defect complexes in silicon at the end of a radiation damage cascade. The calculations described here make use of the equivalent crystal theory of Smith and Banerjea (1). The equivalent crystal theory is a new technique for computing interatomic interactions that has proven both simple enough for use in a computationally intensive application such as molecular dynamics, and accurate enough to correctly predict such properties as surface energies, surface relaxations, surface reconstructions and vacancy relaxations. In our work we report results on the existence of an atomic displacement threshold, the defect formation energy, and some crystallographic information on the defects observed.

INTRODUCTION

Radiation damage is of great interest to NASA and to the space photovoltaic community as it is one of the major factors limiting the lifetimes of photovoltaic systems in space. The general mechanisms of damage are reasonably well-known, but the resulting defects are not completely well-characterized, particularly in III-V compounds such as gallium arsenide, where experimental techniques such as Deep Level Transient Spectroscopy may not yield unambiguous results. To date, empirical parameters such as damage coefficients have been used to roughly characterize the results of the exposure of cells to the space environment (2). Such approaches are of limited utility in that they offer little in the way of fundamental understanding of the damage mechanism, and therefore can do little to point the way for future cell development. At the other extreme, if the crystallographic structure of damaged material is known, the traditional methods of condensed matter theory may be brought to bear, and

information on electronic structure may be obtained (3). To shed additional light on these processes, we have developed a code for a Molecular Dynamics computer simulation of radiation damage and defect production in semiconductors. This approach yields information on the crystallographic structure of the damaged material, and also on the dynamics of the damage. In this paper we present some preliminary results from this work. We have performed our initial work on silicon for the purposes of verifying our model and method, as there is generally more experimental information available on silicon than on III-V compounds.

RADIATION DAMAGE

The radiation damage of interest to the PV community occurs through the interaction of energetic protons and electrons with the semiconductor material. These particles are incident with a wide range of energies, but of primary interest are particles incident with energies in the range of 0.1 MeV to 10 MeV. During the collision of such particles with a semiconductor atom, several interactions can take place:

- (1) Inelastic collisions between the incident particle and the electrons of the semiconductor material.
- (2) Elastic collisions between the incident particle and the nuclei of the semiconductor material, via Rutherford scattering and "hard-sphere" interaction with the nuclei.
- (3) Inelastic collisions between the incident particle and the nuclei of the semiconductor material.

Of these three classes of interaction, those of the first type are responsible for dissipating most of the energy of the incident particle, but interactions of the second type are responsible for most of the damage to the semiconductor. The actual damage occurs primarily through displacement of the semiconductor atoms from their equilibrium positions in the undamaged lattice. Once displaced, a semiconductor atom may collide elastically with other atoms in the lattice, giving rise to a trail of displacements. Kinchin and Pease (4) give an expression

for the number of displacements caused by a primary “knock-on” event initiated by the interaction of an energetic proton with a silicon atom. For the incident proton energies of interest here (0.1 to 10 MeV), they find that each such event results in a total of about 4-6 silicon atom displacements. Once such a defect trail is formed, the displaced atoms will eventually thermalize with the rest of the lattice, and relax to new stable positions which may or may not be at regular lattice positions, forming vacancies and interstitials, along with larger complexes made up of these.

These defects and complexes can degrade the performance of a solar cell, notably through modification of the equilibrium carrier concentration and the minority carrier lifetime.

Such radiation damage events also exhibit a threshold energy below which there is no permanent damage to the semiconductor. For incident electrons, the threshold has been determined experimentally to be 145 keV and 125 keV (5-7). From these results may be calculated a displacement energy, that is, the minimum energy needed to give a silicon atom a permanent displacement in an otherwise perfect crystal. Such a calculation has been performed (with a number of simplifying assumptions) by Seitz and Koehler (8). For silicon, the experimental results correspond to displacement energies of 12.9 and 11.0 eV, respectively (2).

MOLECULAR DYNAMICS

Molecular Dynamics (MD) is a simulation technique which involves the iterated simultaneous solution of the equations of motion for each body in a many-particle system for which the potential energies of interaction (along with suitable boundary conditions) are known. The method produces the time evolution of the configuration of the system, and can be used to study dynamical processes affecting the system. In more detail, the trajectories of individual particles are computed using Newtonian or other mechanics, with interparticle interactions ranging from simple hard-sphere interactions (9) to sophisticated interactions derived from density-functional theory (10). The MD technique has been used since the 1950's, and, indeed, one of its first uses was an early study of radiation damage in copper (11).

In our work, a computational cell is set up in which all atoms are initially in their equilibrium lattice positions. Special boundary conditions are used on the faces of the

computational cell. Periodic boundary conditions are used to compute the interatomic interactions (among atoms within the cell), but atoms which move outside the computational cell are not mapped back into the cell on the opposite face. To do so would be equivalent to allowing the high-velocity incident atom (or atoms scattered at high velocity by the incident one) to make repeated passes through the same region of the crystal, with the result that the damage done would be artificially large. Instead, if any atom travels beyond the boundaries of the cell, it is removed from consideration, and assumed to be beyond the range of interaction for atoms within the cell.

The computation is divided into an “incident” phase and an “anneal” phase. At the start of the incident phase, all atoms are given thermal velocities consistent with a fixed starting temperature (here 50K). To simulate the radiation damage, one atom at one of the cell boundaries is given an incident velocity into the computational cell. The incident velocity is computed assuming that this incident atom has just experienced an elastic collision with an energetic proton.

Following the above initialization, the time evolution of the configuration of atoms in the cell is computed iteratively for each atom in the computational cell as follows.

- (1) The distances to all other atoms are computed, and those neighboring atoms close enough to interact with the atom under consideration are identified.
- (2) The total energy of interaction of the atom with all nearest and second-nearest neighbors is computed using the Equivalent Crystal Theory, with the acceleration of the atom obtained from the energy gradient.
- (3) The acceleration, along with the position, velocity and acceleration from previous timesteps, are used to compute the new values of the position and velocity.

The method used to compute the interaction energies is discussed in the following section.

The equations of motion are integrated numerically using the Beeman algorithm (12). Other workers have used different schemes for the integration, notably predictor-corrector techniques, but these appear to be falling out of favor. The Beeman method has an additional virtue in that it is known to do a better job of conserving energy than

other simple integration schemes such as the widely-used one due to Verlet (13).

Following the incident phase, the anneal phase takes place, in which a “local” energy minimum is determined. The configuration corresponding to this minimum is the one closest to the configuration at the end of the incident section. As such, it is not a global minimum, but represents the metastable configuration of the cell after the damage has taken place. The configuration is determined using one of two methods. In the first method, a target temperature is selected and the average temperature of the cell is computed. If the average temperature is greater than the target temperature, the atom velocities are rescaled so as to relax the average temperature toward the target temperature. In the second method, a simple “simulated annealing” Monte Carlo algorithm is used. Each atom is given a small random displacement. If the total energy of the cell is lower with the atom at this new configuration, the atom is installed at the new position; otherwise, it is moved back to its original position. The method also contains provisions that allow the configuration to escape from a local energy minimum, but we do not make use of this provision, as we are specifically looking for such a local minimum.

INTERACTION POTENTIALS

In order to obtain results from MD codes that are qualitatively and quantitative correct, it is necessary to have an accurate means for computing interatomic interaction energies. In addition, since many of the systems of interest display motion over distances that are large on an atomic scale, computational cells may contain many thousands or even tens of thousands of atoms, and the interatomic energies must be simple and efficient to compute. A large body of work has been done using simple pair potentials, for example, the Lennard-Jones potential (13). This potential, while quite simple, is known to yield structural results for the solids of interest here that are not even qualitatively correct. Another potential method, known as the embedded atom method (EAM) of Foiles, Baskes and Daw (14), has been used by others, for example, Cassenti et al (15), to perform similar simulations. This potential, while more accurate than the Lennard-Jones potential, still yields structural results that, under certain conditions, differ substantially from experiment (1).

Equivalent Crystal Theory

In our computations, interaction potentials are computed using the Equivalent Crystal Theory (ECT) of Smith and Banerjea (1). The ECT method is a semi-empirical method that has been shown to yield highly-accurate structural predictions for a number of systems of interest, notably surface reconstruction, surface relaxation and displacement boundaries. Our previous work involving Monte Carlo and Molecular Dynamics calculations for small systems using ECT is the first such work reported in the literature (16,17).

The ECT method is derived from perturbation theory and is based on the Universal Binding Energy Relation (UBER) of Rose, Ferrante and Smith (18). Briefly, it is found that, with the proper rescaling, the potential energy of interaction of atoms or molecules as a function of interatomic separation falls on the same curve for a wide variety of materials. The UBER has been found to hold for such diverse phenomena as bimetallic adhesion, cohesion in metals, and covalent and metallic bonding in chemisorption. The relation can be expressed as

$$E^*(a^*) = -(1+a^*)e^{-a^*}$$

where $E^*(a^*)$ is the universal energy functional, and a^* is a rescaled length (e.g. the lattice constant or, as used here, the Wigner-Seitz radius) given by

$$a^* = (r_{WS} - r_{WSE})/l$$

in which r_{WS} and r_{WSE} are the Wigner-Seitz radius and equilibrium Wigner-Seitz radii, respectively, and l is a scaling length derived from the bulk modulus and cohesive energy.

The ECT method itself is based on the assumption that the energy of an atom within an arbitrary configuration of neighboring atoms will be the same as the energy of that atom in the “equivalent crystal.” The equivalent crystal has the structure of a perfect crystal of the material of interest, but is dilated (that is, it has an arbitrary lattice constant). It is necessary, then, to find the value of the equivalent crystal lattice constant for which the energy of the equivalent crystal is the same as that of the arbitrary configuration of atoms. To do so, a perturbation expansion for the energy of the arbitrary configuration is performed, in which the energy is written as the sum of the energy of a perfect crystal, and the perturbation energy

due to the deviation of the arbitrary configuration from the perfect crystalline state. This energy is equated with the energy of a perfect, but dilated, crystal of the same material. This equation is then solved for the value of the dilated lattice constant that makes the perturbation vanish. The value of the equivalent crystal lattice constant is rescaled and used in the UBER equation to compute the energy of the arbitrary configuration of atoms. It should be noted that the accuracy of the method can be improved, at the cost of more computation, by retaining more terms in the perturbation expansion.

In this work, the perturbation expansion is truncated, and a simple transcendental equation for the equivalent lattice constant is obtained.

$$N_1 R_{ec}^p e^{-\alpha R_{ec}} + N_2 (c_2 R_{ec}^p) e^{-(\alpha + 1/\lambda) c_2 R_{ec}} - \sum_{\substack{\text{near} \\ \text{neighbors}}} R_j^p e^{-\alpha R_j} - \sum_{\substack{\text{2nd near} \\ \text{neighbors}}} R_j^p e^{-(\alpha + 1/\lambda) R_j} = 0$$

where N_1 and N_2 are the numbers of nearest- and next-nearest neighbors in the perfect crystal, R_{ec} is the equivalent-crystal nearest neighbor distance, R_j is the actual distance to the j^{th} neighbor, $p=2n-2$ where n is the principal quantum number of the atom, c_2 is the ratio between the nearest- and next-nearest neighbor distances in the perfect crystal, α is an electronic wavefunction decay constant, and λ is a next-nearest-neighbor screening constant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two sets of results are presented. First, we investigate the existence of a displacement threshold, that is, an incident velocity below which the atoms of the computational cell exhibit no permanent displacement, and remain in the vicinity of their equilibrium positions before the damage event. Before we offer a working definition of displacement, we must consider exactly what happens to an incident atom. In all the simulations to date, the incident atom is given an initial velocity into the crystal in the (100) direction. The atom is therefore headed directly towards a neighboring atom in the next Wigner-Seitz cell, one lattice constant away. Unless the incident velocity is roughly comparable to the thermal velocities of the other atoms, it is most likely that the incident atom will strike the neighboring atom and recoil back approximately toward its initial location. We consider a permanent displacement to have taken place if

one of the following is true:

- (1) The recoil does not occur, and the atom proceeds out of the Wigner-Seitz cell from which it originated.
- (2) The recoil does occur, but only after the atom has left the Wigner-Seitz cell from which it originated.

These conditions can be justified on energy conservation grounds.

For the diamond lattice the boundary between Wigner-Seitz cells in the (100) direction is located at a displacement of 0.5 lattice constants away from the equilibrium position of the incident atom. It can be seen in Table 1 that, according to the criterion described above, there is an incident velocity between 3×10^{12} Lattice Constants (LC)/sec and 1×10^{13} LC/sec at which the incident atom is sufficiently energetic to undergo a permanent displacement from its initial position. Thus our results are in qualitative agreement with experiment, although our displacement energy (which must lie in the range defined by the above velocities) is somewhat lower than estimates based on Seitz's calculations. We will resolve this discrepancy in future work.

Table 1. Displacement Threshold Results

Incident Velocity, LC/sec	Displacement at time of recoil
1×10^{12}	0.1
2×10^{12}	0.21
3×10^{12}	0.23
1×10^{13}	0.58
2×10^{13}	1.33

Additional evidence for the existence of a displacement threshold is presented in Figures 1a and 1b. In these figures, the displacements of all atoms in the computational cell are displayed, for incident velocities of 2×10^{12} LC/sec (Fig. 1a) and 1×10^{13} LC/sec (Fig. 1b). The histograms represent data taken after an incident phase of approximately 5×10^{-12} seconds duration, and a Monte Carlo simulated anneal phase.

In Fig. 1a it can be seen that the mean displacement is approximately 0.05 LC, a small fraction of the nearest-neighbor separation of 0.433 LC. There are no displacements larger than about 0.15 LC; all atoms in the computational cell remain reasonably close to their initial positions.

Fig. 1a

Fig. 1b

Figure 1. Atomic displacements from equilibrium position for incident velocities of (a) 2×10^{12} LC/sec, and (b) 1×10^{13} LC/sec.

In Fig. 1b, the displacements are substantially larger, with the mean appearing to be in the neighborhood of 0.2 LC. Also of note are the very large displacements of approximately 0.4, 0.53, 0.6 and 0.64 LC. These displacements are on the order of, or greater than, the equilibrium nearest-neighbor separation. Since the computational cell has undergone a simulated anneal, these large displacements most likely are permanent, with the atoms occupying stable or metastable sites. Note that the existence of four large displacements, caused by one incident atom, is consistent with the estimate of Kinchin and Pease previously mentioned.

In addition to the displacement threshold study, we have used the simulated annealing portion of our computer code

to investigate the energetics of two simple defects, the vacancy and divacancy, formed during the simulation. For both defects, we have computed the defect formation energy in unrelaxed and relaxed cases. We find that the unrelaxed defect formation energy is 4.32 eV for the vacancy, and 6.53 eV for the divacancy. In the relaxed case, the energies are 4.28 eV and 6.47 eV, respectively. It should be noted that the actual vacancy formation energy in silicon is somewhat controversial; further, our potential does not adequately describe effects such as the Jahn-Teller distortion that depend on subtle changes in the electronic structure.

CONCLUSIONS AND WORK IN PROGRESS

Our molecular dynamics simulation of radiation damage in silicon displays appropriate behavior in that there is a displacement threshold consistent with experiment, and the number of displacements produced by an incident atom is consistent with the results of other work. In addition, we find qualitative agreement with experiment in that the defects we observe are consistent with those known to exist in radiation-damaged silicon.

Much work remains to be done with regard to characterizing the state of the computational cell after damage, and the defects produced. To that end, we are attempting to generate statistically meaningful numbers of defects through the use of larger computational cells. This will require a faster computer than the current 10 MFLOP-class machine; we are currently porting our computer code to Lewis' Cray Y/MP.

In addition, future calculations will be performed on III-V semiconductors such as Gallium Arsenide and Indium Phosphide. An extended version of ECT has been developed (19) that describes the energetics of multi-component materials, and this new method is being incorporated into the current code.

REFERENCES

1. J. R. Smith and A. Banerjee, Phys. Rev. Lett. 59, 2451 (1987) and Phys. Rev. B 37 10411 (1988).
2. H. Y. Tada, J. R. Carter, Jr., B. E. Anspaugh and R. G. Downing, "Solar Cell Radiation Handbook," Third Edition, NASA JPL Publication 82-69.

3. see, for example, J. Bernholc, N. Lipari and S. Pantelides, "Self-Consistent Method for Point Defects in Semiconductors: Application to the Vacancy in Silicon," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 41, 895 (1978).
4. G. W. Kinchin and R. S. Pease, "The Displacement of Atoms in Solids by Radiation," *Report Prog. Phys.* 18, 1 (1955).
5. J. J. Loferski and P. Rappaport, "Radiation Damage in Ge and Si Detected by Carrier Lifetime Changes--Damage Thresholds," *Phys. Rev.* 111, 432 (1958).
6. H. Flicker, J. J. Loferski and J. Scott-Monck, "Radiation Defect Introduction Rates in n- and p-Type Silicon in the Vicinity of the Radiation Damage Threshold," *Phys. Rev.* 128, 2557 (1962).
7. N. N. Gersimenko et. al., "Threshold Energy for the Formation of Radiation Defects in Semiconductors," *Soviet Physics-Semiconductors* 5, 1439 (1972).
8. F. Seitz and J. S. Koehler, "Displacement of Atoms During Irradiation," *Solid State Physics*, 2, 305 (1956).
9. B. J. Alder and T. E. Wainwright, "Phase Transition for a Hard Sphere System," *J. Chem. Phys.* 27, 1208 (1957).
10. R. Car and M. Parinello, "Unified Approach for Molecular Dynamics and Density-Functional Theory," *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 55, 2471 (1985).
11. J. B. Gibson, A. N. Goland, M. Milgram and G. H. Vineyard, "Dynamics of Radiation Damage," *Phys. Rev.* 120, 1229 (1960).
12. D. Beeman, "Some Multistep Methods for Use in Molecular Dynamics Calculations," *J. Comput. Phys.* 20, 130 (1976).
13. L. Verlet, "Computer 'Experiments' on Classical Fluids. I Thermodynamics Properties of Lennard-Jones Molecules.," *Phys. Rev.* 159, 98 (1967).
14. M. S. Daw and M. I. Baskes, *Phys. Rev. B* 29, 6442 (1984).
15. B. Cassenti, private communication.
16. B. S. Good, A. Banerjea, J. R. Smith, G. H. Bozzolo and J. Ferrante, "Monte Carlo Investigation of Avalanche in Adhesion," *Mat. Res. Soc. Symp. Proc.* (1990).
17. B. S. Good and A. Banerjea, "Molecular Dynamics Investigation of Avalanche in Adhesion," *Bull. Am. Phys. Soc.* 36, 943 (1991).
18. J. H. Rose, J. Ferrante and J. R. Smith, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 47, 675 (1981).
19. G. Bozzolo and J. Ferrante, private communication.